

ReSurveyDunes — a data resource of resurveyed coastal dune vegetation plots in Italy*

Alicia Teresa Rosario Acosta¹, Letizia Di Biase¹, Simona Sarmati¹, Emilia Allevato², Claudia Angiolini³, Simonetta Bagella⁴, Giuseppe Bazan⁵, Andrea Bertacchi⁶, Lisa Brancaleoni⁷, Gabriella Buffa⁸, Mariasole Calbi⁹, Maria Carmela Caria⁴, Daniela Ciccarelli¹⁰, Maurizio Cutini¹, Maria Carla de Francesco^{11,12}, Antonino De Natale², Edy Fantinato⁸, Tiberio Fiaschi³, Carmen Gangale¹³, Renato Gerdol⁷, Lorenzo Gianguzzi^{12,14}, Valentina Lucia Astrid Laface¹⁵, Simona Maccherini^{3,12}, Antonio Morabito¹⁵, Michele Mugnai⁹, Carmelo Maria Musarella¹⁵, Emilia Pafumi^{3,12}, Annalisa Santangelo², Saverio Sciandrello¹⁶, Eugenia Siccardi⁹, Giovanni Spampinato¹⁵, Angela Stanisci^{11,12}, Sandro Strumia¹⁷, Daniele Viciani⁹, Silvia Del Vecchio¹⁸

1 Department of Sciences, University of Rome 3, Rome, Italy

2 Department of Biology, University of Naples "Federico II", Naples, Italy

3 Department of Life Sciences, University of Siena, Siena, Italy

4 Department of Chemical, Physical, Mathematical and Natural Sciences, Università di Sassari, Sassari, Italy

5 Department of Biological, Chemical and Pharmaceutical Sciences and Technologies (STEBICEF), University of Palermo, Palermo, Italy

6 Department of Agricultural, Food and Environmental Sciences, University of Pisa, Pisa, Italy

7 Department of Environmental and Prevention Sciences, University of Ferrara, Ferrara, Italy

8 Department of Environmental Sciences, Informatics and Statistics, Ca' Foscari University of Venice, Venice

9 Department of Biology, University of Florence, Florence, Italy

10 Department of Biology, University of Pisa, Pisa, Italy

11 Department of Biosciences and Territory, Università del Molise, Termoli, Italy

12 NBFC, National Biodiversity Future Center, Palermo, Italy

13 Ministero dell'Ambiente e della Sicurezza Energetica, DG Affari Europei, Internazionali e Finanza Sostenibile, Rome, Italy

14 Department of Agricultural, Food and Forest Sciences, University of Palermo, Palermo, Italy

15 Department of Agraria, University "Mediterranea" of Reggio Calabria, Reggio Calabria, Italy

16 Department of Biological, Geological and Environmental Sciences, University of Catania, Catania, Italy

17 Department of Environmental, Biological and Pharmaceutical Sciences and Technologies, University of Campania "Luigi Vanvitelli", Caserta, Italy

18 BIOME Lab, Department of Biological, Geological and Environmental Sciences - BiGeA, Alma Mater Studiorum University of Bologna, Bologna, Italy

Corresponding author: Letizia Di Biase (letizia.dibiase@uniroma3.it)

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Abstract

We present ReSurveyDunes — the first database of Italian coastal dune vegetation plots, developed through a collaborative network of Italian vegetation scientists. This paper describes the scope of the initiative, provides an overview of the available data, and highlights its key features, research applications, and future potential.

ReSurveyDunes currently comprises 972 vegetation plots distributed across 11 Italian regions (Abruzzo, Basilicata, Calabria, Campania, Emilia-Romagna, Lazio, Molise, Sardinia, Sicily, Tuscany, and Veneto). The original plots were surveyed between 1974 and 2009, with a primary focus on herbaceous psammophilous coastal zonation (habitats 1210, 2110, 2120, 2130*, 2210, 2230, and 2240, as defined by the 92/43/EEC Habitats Directive). Resurveys were conducted in 2023 and 2024. Each plot dataset

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includes (i) a complete list of vascular plant species with cover estimates; (ii) geographic coordinates (latitude and longitude); (iii) sampling dates; and (iv) plot size.

Designed to analyze fine-scale temporal trends in Italian coastal vegetation, ReSurveyDunes is a versatile tool for diverse ecological studies. It represents a valuable resource for evidence-based decision-making, enabling targeted conservation and management actions informed by up-to-date ecological data.

Keywords

Coastal dune habitats, Habitats Directive, psammophilous vegetation, resurvey, temporal trends, vegetation database

Introduction

According to the 4th Report under article 17 of the EU Habitats Directive 92/43/EEC (EEC 1992), the conservation status of Italian coastal sand dunes habitats is worryingly bad: the overall assessment reports 89% of habitats in Unfavorable Bad conservation status while the remaining 11% is reported as Unfavorable Inadequate (Prisco et al. 2020; Ercole et al. 2021). This critically poor conservation state has been assessed across all criteria and Biogeographical Regions, and it is particularly serious for key dune habitats that provide essential ecosystem services, such as “Shifting dunes with *Ammophila arenaria*”, which are considered crucial for dune formation and protection against coastal erosion (La Bella et al. 2024). Even more alarmingly, the conservation status of Italian coastal dune habitats mirrors that of the broader Mediterranean biogeographical region (Janssen et al. 2016). Main pressures and threats stem from increasing human activities, including the development of residential, commercial, and industrial areas, as well as the expansion of alien and ruderal species (Géhu and Biondi 1994; Janssen et al. 2016; Gao et al. 2020; Prisco et al. 2020; Singh et al. 2021).

Plot-based vegetation samples, known as vegetation plots, document plant species diversity and community composition at specific locations and times. Resurveying studies, which involve re-sampling historically surveyed vegetation plots, are increasingly being used to detect temporal changes in the vegetation of various ecosystems (Knollová et al. 2024). These studies predominantly rely on phytosociological data due to the long tradition of phytosociological relevés and the recent compilation of large repositories that provide invaluable data across a variety of habitats (Dengler et al. 2011; Chytrý et al. 2016; Sabatini et al. 2021). Despite some degree of relocation error, revisitation studies are considered a valid and cost-effective tool for analysing temporal dynamics in plant communities (Hédl et al. 2017; Kapfer et al. 2017).

In Italy, resurveying coastal dune habitats has proven highly effective for identifying major temporal trends at both community and species levels. Del Vecchio et al. (2015a, 2015b) focused on resurveying phytoso-

logical relevés, while Sperandii et al. (2019, 2021) based their resurveying on georeferenced random plots. However, all these studies have been conducted in relatively restricted areas or regions, and thus, no temporal trends on coastal dune vegetation at a wide-scale are currently available.

The great diversity of Italian coastal dune habitats has been widely recognized (Brullo et al. 2001; Biondi et al. 2009; Prisco et al. 2013). This relevant diversity, coupled with the undoubtedly poor conservation status of these fragile but resilient habitats (Santoro et al. 2012), underscores the need for more effective conservation measures. Such measures should be supported by detailed knowledge of biodiversity temporal trends preferentially derived from wide-scale monitoring activities, both inside and outside protected areas. Therefore, reliable estimates of long-term vegetation changes in these threatened habitats are urgently needed at the national level.

In this context, we introduce ReSurveyDunes — a new data resource of resurveyed coastal dune vegetation plots in Italy, compiled by a collaborative network of Italian vegetation scientists. This is the first database of Italian coastal dune resurveyed vegetation, collecting historical phytosociological information revisited during 2023/2024. Here, we provide an overview of the currently available data, illustrating the main characteristics of the database and its potential future uses.

Database compilation

In 2023, a call for collaboration was sent to vegetation experts of the Italian Society of Vegetation Science (SISV) to join the ReSurveyDune project, aiming to resurvey Italian coastal dune areas as comprehensively as possible. To be included in ReSurveyDune, all datasets needed to meet the following minimum requirements: (i) a complete list of vascular plants within defined plots, including information on species cover; (ii) plot location data, including longitude and latitude, along with information on the precision of the coordinates (specified geographic accuracy level); (iii) sampling date; and (iv) plot size.

Database structure, content taxonomic standardization and limitations

Overall, ReSurveyDune currently includes 972 vegetation plots located in 11 Italian administrative regions Abruzzo, Basilicata, Calabria, Campania, Emilia-Romagna, Lazio, Molise, Sardinia, Sicily, Tuscany, and Veneto (Fig. 1). The historical dataset includes a total of 495 plots, comprising both published phytosociological vegetation records and additional unpublished data, all of which were revisited (Suppl. materials 1, 2 for detailed references and for the distribution of each habitat). Therefore, for each plot, the outcome of the revisitation is provided, and the plots that could not be located or that disappeared were marked as such. Sampling size varied from 1 to 450 m², but was

relatively homogeneous within each habitat type. Resurveying was performed in 2023 and 2024 with the same approach as for the historical plots, during the same season and with the same plot size. The occurrence of all vascular plant species was recorded, and species abundance was visually estimated using the Braun-Blanquet percentage cover scale (Braun-Blanquet 1964), as in historical plots. Taxonomic nomenclature was standardised according to Euro+Med 2006 database.

At this stage, we have included only herbaceous-champhytic coastal dune habitats, although we plan to incorporate woody dune habitats in future updates. Each relevé has been assigned to a specific EU habitat type (as defined by the 92/43/EEC Habitats Directive; EEC 1992). Seven habitats were considered (Table 1): 1210, 2110, 2120, 2130* (priority habitat), 2210, 2230, and 2240 (Biondi et al. 2009), corresponding to three

Figure 1. Distribution of resurveyed historical vegetation plots across 11 Italian administrative regions. Each green dot represents plot location. Black dots represent major cities with their names labelled.

Table 1. Summary of coastal EU habitats included in the database. For each habitat type, the EUNIS and Habitats Directive (Annex I) code and name, a brief description with most frequent species, and the number and the mean area per habitat of historical plots are provided.

EUNIS code and name	Habitats Directive code and name (Annex I)	Habitat description	Number of historical plots	Mean area per habitat (m ²)	Most frequent species
N12 Mediterranean and Black Sea sandy beaches	1210 Annual vegetation of drift lines	Pioneer communities of therophytic-salinophytic species	87	43.7	<i>Cakile maritima</i> <i>Xanthium orientale</i> <i>Thynopyrum junceum</i>
N14 Coastal mobile dune habitats of the Mediterranean, Macaronesia, and Black Sea	2110 Embryonic shifting dunes	Pioneer communities of perennial species dominated by <i>Elymus farctus</i> ssp. <i>farctus</i>	156	33.3	<i>Thynopyrum junceum</i> <i>Eryngium maritimum</i> <i>Echinophora spinosa</i>
	2120 Shifting dunes along the shoreline with <i>Ammophila arenaria</i> (white dunes)	Semi-permanent cordons of the dune system dominated by <i>Ammophila arenaria</i> ssp. <i>australis</i>	154	45.3	<i>Calamagrostis arenaria</i> <i>Echinophora spinosa</i> <i>Eryngium maritimum</i>
	2130* Fixed coastal dunes with herbaceous vegetation (grey dunes)	Fixed dunes, stabilised and colonised by more or less closed perennial grasslands and abundant carpets of lichens and mosses	1	25	<i>Helianthemum nummularium</i> <i>Thymus pulegioides</i> <i>Catapodium rigidum</i>
N16 Mediterranean and Macaronesian coastal dune grasslands (grey dunes)	2210 <i>Crucianellion maritimae</i> fixed beach dunes	Fixed dunes with chamaephytic communities dominated by <i>Crucianella maritima</i> and <i>Pancreatium maritimum</i>	54	45	<i>Pancreatium maritimum</i> <i>Thynopyrum junceum</i> <i>Eryngium maritimum</i>
	2230 <i>Malcolmietalia</i> dune grasslands	Fixed dunes with therophytic grasslands	40	37.9	<i>Festuca fasciculata</i> <i>Cyperus capitatus</i> <i>Lagurus ovatus</i>
	2240 <i>Brachypodietalia</i> dune grasslands with annuals	Dune mediterranean xeric grasslands rich in therophytes	3	7.33	<i>Aira elegans</i> <i>Anthemis arvensis</i> <i>Cerastium ligusticum</i>

Figure 2. Number of historical vegetation plots originally surveyed across different time periods, grouped in 5-year intervals (except the last interval, which spans 6 years), and categorized by habitat type (as defined by the 92/43/EEC Directive).

EUNIS habitat types N12, N14, N16 (<https://eunis.eea.europa.eu/habitats>). The number of vegetation plots per habitat is shown in Fig. 2. The oldest historical plot dates to 1974, while the most recent one was recorded in 2009. As the original data (historical plots) were

sampled for various purposes using the phytosociological approach, despite harmonisation of basic attributes upon integrating the datasets into ReSurveyDunes, there remains variation in relevant features such as plot location accuracy and plot size.

Data accessibility

ReSurveyDunes is an independent resurvey database, with data ownership retained by the contributors. Decisions on data sharing will be made individually for each data request. By the end of the ReSurveyDune project, we plan to integrate this database into larger data repositories to ensure easy access and interoperability of the data. One such repository is ReSurveyEurope, which is currently being developed and is closely connected to the European Vegetation Archive, EVA (Knollová et al. 2024).

Application and future perspectives

In this article, we introduced ReSurveyDunes, the first Italian dataset of fine-scale resurveyed coastal dune vegetation habitats. This dataset provides a comprehensive overview of the diversity of Italian coastal dune habitats and serves as a crucial tool for analysing temporal changes in these fragile ecosystems at a national scale.

Because the vegetation plots are georeferenced, they can be integrated with additional information (i.e. remote sensing data), facilitating the analysis of a wide range of impacts, including human pressure, coastal erosion, alien species invasion, or climatic changes. Additionally, the plot records can be overlaid with protected area boundaries to identify major conservation gaps. They can also be used to pinpoint priority areas for future surveys. Moreover, the information in this dataset can support the evaluation of changes in the conservation status of Annex I habitats, as required by the Habitats Directive.

Overall, ReSurveyDunes not only offers a valuable resource for studying coastal dune vegetation dynamics and their responses to environmental changes, enhancing our understanding of these highly threatened habitats, but also contributes to informed decision-making for habitat conservation and management.

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Supplementary material 1

References for the historical plots

Authors: Alicia Teresa Rosario Acosta, Letizia Di Biase, Simona Sarmati, Emilia Allevato, Claudia Angiolini, Simonetta Bagella, Giuseppe Bazan, Andrea Bertacchi, Lisa Brancaleoni, Gabriella Buffa, Mariasole Calbi, Maria Carmela Caria, Daniela Ciccarelli, Maurizio Cutini, Maria Carla de Francesco, Antonino De Natale, Edy Fantinato, Tiberio Fiaschi, Carmen Gangale, Renato Gerdol, Lorenzo Gianguzzi, Valentina Lucia Astrid Laface, Simona Maccherini, Antonio Morabito, Michele Mugnai, Carmelo Maria Musarella, Emilia Pafumi, Annalisa Santangelo, Saverio Sciandrello, Eugenia Siccardi, Giovanni Spampinato, Angela Stanisci, Sandro Strumia, Daniele Viciani, Silvia Del Vecchio

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Supplementary material 2

Distribution maps

Authors: Alicia Teresa Rosario Acosta, Letizia Di Biase, Simona Sarmati, Emilia Allevato, Claudia Angiolini, Simonetta Bagella, Giuseppe Bazan, Andrea Bertacchi, Lisa Brancaleoni, Gabriella Buffa, Mariasole Calbi, Maria Carmela Caria, Daniela Ciccarelli, Maurizio Cutini, Maria Carla de Francesco, Antonino De Natale, Edy Fantinato, Tiberio Fiaschi, Carmen Gangale, Renato Gerdol, Lorenzo Gianguzzi, Valentina Lucia Astrid Laface, Simona Maccherini, Antonio Morabito, Michele Mugnai, Carmelo Maria Musarella, Emilia Pafumi, Annalisa Santangelo, Saverio Sciandrello, Eugenia Siccardi, Giovanni Spampinato, Angela Stanisci, Sandro Strumia, Daniele Viciani, Silvia Del Vecchio

Data type: tif

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